

A Study on Recruitment Process of Competent Employees at Lumina Datamatics

Vinod. T, Karthik. S, Ranjith Kumar. S

MBA Student, Rajiv Gandhi College of Engineering and Technology, Puducherry, India

ABSTRACT

The “competence recruitment process” is a process of recruitment based on the ability of candidates to produce anecdotes about their professional experience which can be used as evidence that the candidate has a given competency. “A study on effective recruitment process of competent employees at Lumina Datamatics Limited, Puducherry” aimed to find out the existing recruitment process and satisfaction level of employees in the organization. The total population for the study is 120 and the sample size is 60. The type of sample design used for the study is simple random sampling. Primary data was used for the study primary data was collected by using questionnaire. The gathered information is critically analysed by using various statistical tools like Karl Pearson coefficient of correlation to arrive at a meaningful conclusion. From the study, by using Karl Pearson Coefficient of Correlation it was found that there is a significant relationship between age of the employees and competence recruitment process.

KEYWORDS: Recruitment, competence, existing recruitment process, employee’s satisfaction.

How to cite this paper: Vinod. T | Karthik. S | Ranjith Kumar. S "A Study on Recruitment Process of Competent Employees at Lumina Datamatics" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-6, October 2019, pp.458-461, URL: <https://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd29130.pdf>

Copyright © 2019 by author(s) and International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development Journal. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

INTRODUCTION

In human resource management, “Recruitment” is the process of finding and hiring the best and most qualified candidate for a job opening, in a timely and cost-effective manner. It can also be defined as the “process of searching for prospective employees and stimulating and encouraging them to apply for jobs in an organization”.

It is one whole process, with a full life cycle, that begins with identification of the needs of the company with respect to the job, and ends with the introduction of the employee to the organization.

When we speak of the recruitment process, we immediately think of activities such as the analysis of the requirements of a specific job, attracting candidates to apply for that job, screening the applicants and selecting among them, hiring the chosen candidates to become new employees of the organization, and integrating them into the structure.

Obviously, the main reason why the recruitment process is implemented is to find the persons who are best qualified for the positions within the company, and who will help them towards attaining organizational goals. But there are other reasons why a recruitment process is important.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Holzer, 1987 & Hung, 2006, Hiring in the firm generally consists of two sets of activities. One set involves

recruitment of applicants, while the second set involves screening and selection from among these applicants. Past literature treated recruitment and selection as a combined (Shen & Edwards, 2004 Carless, 2007). However, if the applicant pool is inappropriate for the vacancy in the recruitment process, the effectiveness of the selection process becomes limited. Selection is the last phase of the recruitment activity (Giovanni, etal, 1995) and the terms “recruitment and selection” are generally considered to be fully interrelated processes.

A significant amount of literature has shown that a sound recruiting exercise yields high quality employees through a good selection method and can better predict future job performance (Gable, Hollon, & Dangelo, 1992 Heraty & Morley, 1998 Mark, 1995, Murphy & Shiarella, 1997 Cascio, 1998). In addition, competency can effectively leverage individual team and organizational performance (Carroll & McCrackin, 1998). Furthermore from the researcher’s perspective, because the unstable environment, as well the environmental pressure, the organizations must attain premium recruitment and selection process to attain competence and professional staff (Promís, 2008 Brown, 2007). It is also true in terms of success of work performance and perceived quality (Sangeetha, 2010), and the creation of a true competitive advantage for organizations (Van Birgelen, Wetzels, & (Van Dolen, 2008). Many firms, therefore, spend millions of dollars in their

efforts to recruit and select the best employee (Blackman, 2006).

The literature outlines several scientific terms of the outcome of recruitment and selection processes. For the recruitment and selection, previous studies often focused on the employee turnover (Bishop, 2005), performance (Breugh, 1981, Schmidt & Hunter 1998), and quality terms (Williams, Labig, & Stone, 1993, Breugh, et al. 2003). Little attention was considered for the employee workplace competence in the recruitment and selection outcome. However, these competencies were heavily considered during the recruitment and selection criteria under the competence based recruitment and selection literature (Grigoryev, 2006, Reio Jr & Sutton 2006, Snyder, Rupp & Thornton 2006, Keep and James, 2010).

The Competence Definitions

The literature discussed a wide range of definitions for competence. (Spencer and Spencer 1993) defined a competency as “an underlying characteristic of an individual that is causally related to ... superior performance in a job or situation”. Also competencies are attributes, specific constellation of an individual’s characteristics such as knowledge, skills, motives, traits, behaviour, aspects of one’s self-image or social role, or attitudes that gives someone the potential for effective task performance (Vorgelegt von, 2008). It is also a range of capabilities that enable some people to meet the desired behaviour or a range of work demands more effectively than others (Kurz and Bartram, 2002). As well (Carroll & McCrackin 1998) definition include “competencies are knowledge, skills, characterize excellent performance within a specific context”.

Additionally, (Promís 2008) integrated between quality and competence terms, since he utilized the terms as synonym, while conducting the “qualified” people to indicate candidates have the highest degree of the competencies.

A number of studies consider competence and competency to be similar (Sanghi, 2004). It was also demonstrated the definitions of competencies was conducted synonymously. (Cumming, et al., 2009) illustrates that such as a plethora of terms is in common usage, a number of which are used synonymously and interchangeably, and the meaning of skills is utilized to indicate numerous terms. Examples include skills, competence, attribute, quality, ability, capacity and capability. As well, (Reidy 2004) utilized the term of skill or quality terms as synonymous. Along with the notion of competence, this definition has been used in many themes to describe levels of skills and knowledge as applied to concrete work situations (Sicilia, García-Barriocanal, & Alcalde 2005, Vorgelegt Von 2008, Andrews and Higson

2008, Richens, 1999). Some authors (Goodstein and Davidson, 1998) uses both terms synonymously and equal competencies are the knowledge, skills and abilities that are needed for a particular task or job (Ree, Carretta, & Steindl, 2001, von Vorgelegt, 2008). Moreover, (Evers & Rush 1996) and (Williams 2005) were considering competence is utilized to be synonymous with skill.

Accordingly, drawing from the definition adopted by (Cumming, et al., 2009, Tymon 2011, De La Harpe, Radloff and Wyber 2000, Jonson 2011, Moore, Cheng, & Dainty, 2002). “competence” as defined for the purpose of this research a concept that describes the behavioural prerequisites for job performance and organizational results, indicated by skills attribute, character, quality, ability, capacity and capability. The study will consider the definition as a competence concept that describes the behavioural prerequisites for job performance at workplace and organizational results, indicating skills, character, attribute, quality, ability, capacity and capability. As according to the objective of this study, the study will take into consideration the illustration of a variety of competencies definitions that are used synonymously.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To analyse the recruitment process of competent employees followed in LUMINA DATAMATICS PUDUCHERRY.
2. To identify the employees satisfaction with the existing recruitment process of the company.
3. To find the significant relationship between the age of the employee with competence recruitment process.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

H0: There is no significant relationship between age of the employee and competence recruitment process.

Ha: There is a significant relationship between age of the employee and competence recruitment process.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A research design is a plan that specifies the objectives of the study, method to adopt in the collection of data, tool in analysis of data and helpful to frame hypothesis. A research design is arrangement of condition for collections and analysis of data in a manner that aims to combine relevance to research purpose with economy in procedure. A research design is needed because it facilitates the smooth sailing of the various project operations, thereby making the project as efficient towards yielding maximum information with minimum expenditure of effort, time and money. It also minimizes bias and maximizes the reliability of the data collected.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION USING KARL PEARSON COEFFICIENT OF CORRELATION

X	Y	X-x	Y-y	(X-x)(Y-y)	(X-x) ²	(Y-y) ²	(X-x) ² (Y-y) ²
1	34	-1.1	1.5	-1.65	1.21	2.25	2.7225
3	34	0.9	1.5	1.35	0.81	2.25	1.8225
2	34	-0.1	1.5	-0.15	0.01	2.25	0.0225
1	22	-1.1	-10.5	11.55	1.21	110.25	133.4025
3	36	0.9	3.5	3.15	0.81	12.25	9.9225
4	25	1.9	-7.5	-14.25	3.61	56.25	203.0625
2	44	-0.1	11.5	-1.15	0.01	132.25	1.3225
2	36	-0.1	3.5	-0.35	0.01	12.25	0.1225
3	33	0.9	0.5	0.45	0.81	0.25	0.2025

4	31	1.9	-1.5	-2.85	3.61	2.25	8.1225
3	35	0.9	2.5	2.25	0.81	6.25	5.0625
1	33	-1.1	0.5	-0.55	1.21	0.25	0.3025
1	33	-1.1	0.5	-0.55	1.21	0.25	0.3025
2	29	-0.1	-3.5	0.35	0.01	12.25	0.1225
1	32	-1.1	-0.5	0.55	1.21	0.25	0.3025
3	31	0.9	-1.5	-1.35	0.81	2.25	1.8225
2	30	-0.1	-2.5	0.25	0.01	6.25	0.0625
1	29	-1.1	-3.5	3.85	1.21	12.25	14.8225
2	31	-0.1	-1.5	0.15	0.01	2.25	0.0225
3	29	0.9	-3.5	-3.15	0.81	12.25	9.9225
3	26	0.9	-6.5	-5.85	0.81	42.25	34.2225
1	28	-1.1	-4.5	4.95	1.21	20.25	24.5025
1	32	-1.1	-0.5	0.55	1.21	0.25	0.3025
3	31	0.9	-1.5	-1.35	0.81	2.25	1.8225
1	37	-1.1	4.5	-4.95	1.21	20.25	24.5025
1	26	-1.1	-6.5	7.15	1.21	42.25	51.1225
1	35	-1.1	2.5	-2.75	1.21	6.25	7.5625
3	40	0.9	7.5	6.75	0.81	56.25	45.5625
3	36	0.9	3.5	3.15	0.81	12.25	9.9225
2	43	-0.1	10.5	-1.05	0.01	110.25	1.1025
$\sum X=x=63$	$\sum Y=y=975$			$\sum(X-x)(Y-y)=4.5$			$\sum(X-x)^2(Y-y)^2 = 594.095$

Coefficient of correlation

$$r = \frac{\sum (X-x) (Y-y)}{\sqrt{\sum(X-x)^2 \sum (Y-y)^2}}$$

$$r = \frac{4.5}{24.4}$$

$$R = 0.2$$

T test = $\frac{r \sqrt{(n-2)}}{1-r^2}$

$$R = 0.2$$

$$N = 30$$

$$= 0.2 \times \frac{\sqrt{30-2}}{1-(0.2)^2}$$

$$= 5.4$$

The value of coefficient of correlation is 0.2 and T test value is 5.4. This shows that there exists a low degree positive correlation between age of the employees and competence recruitment process. Hence we reject the null hypothesis and accept alternative hypothesis. It was found that there is relationship between age of the employees and competence recruitment process.

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSION

The process of competency based recruitment is intended to be fairer than other recruitment processes by clearly laying down the required competencies and then testing them in such a way that the recruiter has little discretion to favour one candidate over another. Competence recruitment process can result in increased profitability and performance, Attract higher quality candidates and reduce attrition and improve productivity.

The employees are satisfied with the existing recruitment process at Lumina Datamatics Limited. It was found that by using Karl Pearson correlation test, there is a significant

relationship between age of the employee and competence recruitment process.

REFERENCE

- [1] Lin, B. W., Hung, S. C., & Li, P. C. (2006). Mergers and acquisitions as a human resource strategy: Evidence from US banking firms. *International Journal of Manpower*, 27(2), 126-142.
- [2] Shen & Edwards, 2004 Carless, 2007 Shen, H., & Kim, J. N. (2012). Linking ethics congruence, communication strategies, and relationship building. *Public Relations Journal*, 6(3), 1-35.
- [3] Heraty, N., & Morley, M. (1995). Line managers and human resource development. *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 19(10), 31-37.
- [4] Carroll, A. & McCrackin, J. (1998). The Competent Use of Competency Based Strategies for Selecting and Development. *Performance Improvement Quarterly*, 11 (3) 45-63. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1937-8327.1998>.

- [5] Shapiro, S. L., Astin, J. A., Bishop, S. R., & Cordova, M. (2005). Mindfulness-based stress reduction for health care professionals: results from a randomized trial. *International journal of stress management*, 12(2), 164.
- [6] Williams, C. R., Labig, C. E., & Stone, T. H. (1993). Recruitment sources and posthire outcomes for job applicants and new hires: A test of two hypotheses. *Journal of applied psychology*, 78(2), 163.
- [7] Rupp, D. E., Snyder, L. A., Mitchell Gibbons, A., & Thornton III, G. C. (2006). What should developmental assessment centers be developing?. *The Psychologist-Manager Journal*, 9(2), 75-98.
- [8] Kurz, R., & Bartram, D. (2002). Competency and individual performance: Modelling the world of work. *Organisational effectiveness: The role of Psychology*. Wiley. Pp227-258.
- [9] Faculty of Education, Khon Kaen University, Thailand. Promís, P. (2008). Are Employers Asking for the Right Competencies? A Case for Emotional Intelligence. *Essential soft skills*. Library journal, 138(3), 39. Vick, S., & Scott, A., (1998)
- [10] Doh, J. P., Smith, R. R., Stumpf, S. A., & Tymon Jr, W. G. (2011). Pride and professionals: retaining talent in emerging economies. *Journal of business strategy*, 32(5), 35-42.
- [11] Cullen, F. T., Jonson, C. L., & Nagin, D. S. (2011). Prisons do not reduce recidivism: The high cost of ignoring science. *The Prison Journal*, 91(3_suppl), 48S-65S.

